

**CERTIFICATE
OF ACCEPTANCE**

This is to certify that the article authored by **Yo'ldoshev Jasurxo'ja** entitled **“Zamonaviy trikotaj mashinalarining naqshli press trikotaj to‘qimalarini olishdagi texnologik imkoniyatlarini tahlil qilish”**, has been reviewed and officially accepted for publication in International Online Multidisciplinary Conference: Science, Education & Future Trends Bulletin.

The editorial board acknowledges the scientific value of the submitted work and confirms its inclusion in the forthcoming issue of the journal.

Date of Acceptance: 25.12.2025

Editorial Board

IOMS-2025

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Multidisciplinary Conference*

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